

TRANSFORMING NAVAL WARFARE THROUGH UNMANNED TECHNOLOGY: A CASE STUDY OF UKRAINE

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Abstract

Evolution and incorporation of unmanned systems in naval warfare has resulted in a major shift from conventional naval warfare. This is evident in the current Russia-Ukraine conflict. Unmanned or uncrewed systems, overall, indicate a transformative advance in the naval technology and it is attracting significant investments as well as developments around the world. As autonomous systems continuous to reshape the naval warfare, the whole naval community around the world is at the peak point of a new era of defense and conflict. Keeping in view the current technological development and trends of increasing use of unmanned systems, this paper will focus to identify that how these unmanned technologies has changed the conventional mindset of naval warfare, and how Ukraine used these unmanned systems and caused Russia's Black Sea Fleet pull out of the Ukraine's naval unmanned assets reach.

INTRODUCTION

Naval warfare is constantly evolving and has undergone significant changes with technological upgradation drawing attention towards the unmanned systems. Traditional approaches of solving issues and problems have been replaced by new ideas and advanced technologies. In this regard, naval warfare domain has been continuously evolving with due introduction of unmanned systems offering unparalleled capabilities and strategies in reconnaissance, surveillance, naval combat, etc. making them indispensable for modern navies. Unmanned platforms such as Unmanned Surface Vehicles (USVs), Unmanned Underwater Vehicles (UUVs) and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) are reshaping or transforming naval warfare with enhanced capabilities that were once imaginable. This technological advancement has increased the operational flexibility, reduced risk to personnel and

more cost-effective solutions for combat during naval operations. So, when it comes to fighting in 21st century, it is obvious that the unmanned systems are transforming warfare.

The increased reliance on the unmanned systems in naval combat has pushed back the boundaries of conventional or traditional ways of warfare. The strategic advantages of the unmanned technologies are clear, for instance, drones offer accuracy and precision and they are also not susceptible to human errors, carry out precision strikes against high value targets. Similarly, these unmanned systems are advantageous in the high-risk environments, like in contested waters or regions of intense conflict. They also operate without putting human life in danger and provide real-time intelligence.

For these reasons, countries are showing interest of acquiring unmanned technology and they also have

invested accordingly. Because, it is evident that the forces who use these unmanned technologies in naval operations are not only successful in reducing the casualties of their own servicemen but also prevent escalation of the conflict through the limited collateral damage. Some of the recent upgradation and advancements in the field of naval combat systems include unmanned systems, hypersonic, quantum technology, directed energy weapons and conventional missiles.

Many countries with significant navies in the contemporary world are now making investments in developing the unmanned technologies. At least 40 states, at this stage, have unmanned vehicle programs. As more countries are moving towards acquiring the unmanned technologies and unmanned systems, this has caused the emergence of a modern arms race termed as drone arms race. As a consequence of this 'drone arms race', more and more countries are striving for 'roboticization' of their navies, with navies not only steadily 'roboticising' the present functions but also increasingly investing in the research domain in order to gain more technological advantages over other countries.

Presently, unmanned vessels have varying capabilities to operate without supervision, but they all require some level of the human involvement. Taking into considerations the growing advancements in the unmanned technologies, it can be predicted that a world having fully autonomous weapons is not far away. Overall, it is comprehensible that the emergence of unmanned maritime or naval systems has the potential to become a destabilizing force in the international affairs. Over the past decade, the types and quantities of the unmanned systems acquired by various Military Departments have grown, and their capacities or capabilities have become integral to the warfighter operations.

This study uses the case study of Ukraine's use of unmanned technology in the black sea against Russia. The war in Ukraine has made this clear that how much new technology, especially the inexpensive unmanned systems, can be successful and effective against an enemy that is not prepared for them. Ukraine has attacked and damaged many Russian ships including Russia flagship Moskva using unmanned systems, particularly the USVs, and

mines delivered by the low-slung craft that is small in size like the size of a small fishing boat. The Ukraine's unmanned vessels or drones caused much damage to Russia and also pushed Russia far from its coast.

The effectiveness of the unmanned operations of Ukraine in the Black Sea has convinced the International military observers to rethink about the future of naval warfare or naval conflict. The shift towards the use of unmanned technologies has significant ramifications for how the navies of the whole world will approach the maritime security, naval combat as well as the deterrence in the coming years. This use of unmanned vessels by Ukraine has also prompted Russia to respond by developing its own unmanned technologies and vessels along with enhancing its defense capabilities against these emerging threats.

This paper answers two main questions: How does the integration of unmanned systems in naval warfare transform the overall nature of modern naval combat? And What operational advantages do un-manned naval assets offer Ukraine's naval forces in comparison to traditional naval assets in the Black Sea?

Significance:

The significance of this research paper is that it explores the role of the unmanned technologies in remaking the naval warfare. As this research paper focused on the case study of the Ukraine's use of unmanned systems against Russia in the Black Sea which is an ongoing conflict, so this research is timely because the unmanned technologies could play a pivotal role in shaping the security dynamics of the region. This research is also significant because the topic is explored through the lens of the technological determinism theory, that explains that how these technologies transformed the naval warfare and reshape the way states adopt their naval strategies in the Black Sea.

Literature Review:

BURSUC, MUNTEANU, & RUS (2024) describes the evolution of drones in the naval domain, their importance in naval operations and how they will impact the future of naval warfare. He highlights the historical development of the Sea drones that firstly

they were only used for simple objectives like basic observation and surveillance but they evolve with the passage of time and now they are actively involved in the maritime operations causing the transformation of naval warfare. Because these unmanned systems especially the Unmanned Underwater Vessels and Unmanned Surface Vessels provide significant advantages as compare to the traditional naval assets. Now these systems are widely used by states because they carry out operation without risking human lives, along with provide precision of strikes, reduced cost of operations, etc. More states are trying to acquire drones that is causing the remaking of the modern naval warfare.

Imura (2024) explores the legality of the use or the status of the unmanned maritime technology under UNCLOS. Firstly, it is important to inquire that these unmanned systems whether can be termed as warships or not under UNCLOS. He argues that treating unmanned technologies or systems as the warships, there is dire need to examine that whether they meet the definitions of the of a warship or not under the UNCLOS. Imura highlights in his paper that there should be proper international agreements and rules made and followed for the use of the unmanned vessels and fully autonomous systems require further legal clarifications for the use in the naval operations. He concludes with the argument that the navies that want to use the autonomous or unmanned systems should primarily critically evaluate the desired mission and that how they are going to manage the requirements of command and crew particularly during the use of fully autonomous systems.

Dunley (2023) highlights that the Uncrewed Surface Vessels (USVs), although, provide significant advantages to the navies, especially during warfighting, but there is also the need for taking into consideration the technological challenges as well. He argues that the USVs provide many benefits like they are cost-effective, reduce crew sizes, provide greater capabilities. But these Uncrewed Surface Vessels cannot replace the crewed vessels completely. He describes that this is quite unrealistic to replace the crewed vessels with the USVs and also critiques the U.S. Navy's vision of the Uncrewed Surface Vessels (USVs) as the systems that can effectively replace the crewed vessels or platforms. Complete

dependence on the autonomous systems will have benefits but there would be disadvantages of this as well. He describes that, doing this, the states will lose their strategic value and also their capabilities of conducting the maritime peace operations will be undermined. So, there is the need for USVs to complement rather than replace these crewed vessels.

Theoretical Framework:

Although Thorstein Veblen and Marshall McLuhan coined the core ideas of the Technological determinism theory, these ideas are very closely connected with the ideas of Karl Marx. This theory suggest that the technologies drive the development in the human lives as well as the society. This means that when a technology is newly introduced it affect or change the way individuals and the societies act. Because a new technology may lead towards changings in the institutions and power dynamics as well. (Hauer, 2017)

Technological determinism Theory is applied in order to evaluate that how the unmanned technologies like sea drones, UUVs, UAVs, USVs, etc., influence the ways states conduct naval operations and that how these technologies are shaping the future of the naval conflict. As these technologies are continuously growing and their use is expanding and further transforming the warfare, this theory can help in explaining the ways in which these emerging technologies can influence and shift the naval as well as maritime strategies and the global power structures.

Methodology:

Analytical and qualitative approach is followed during the research. The data and information have been collected through secondary sources including scholarly articles, journals, policy documents, books, and different websites. These sources are analyzed to propose effective recommendations.

EVOLUTION OF UNMANNED SYSTEMS IN NAVAL WARFARE:

The formation and use of unmanned systems in naval domain is not a new phenomenon, rather it has long and complex history. Traditional naval warfare was evident of the increased human risk in the most dangerous and hazardous environment and

this has increased the need for the development of the unmanned naval technology for not only preserving the human life but also maintaining the operational effectiveness (Youvan, 2024). In 1960s, the first drones were developed that were used basically for the purpose of data collection as well as transfer. So, it is clear that basically the unmanned technology received increased attention during cold war. That was the start states started thinking about the development of unmanned systems. This was the period that laid the foundations of unmanned technology that later on supported the transition towards more advanced systems. After that in 1970s, states started exploring the potential of unmanned systems or drones and “Torpedes”-the first true drones, were also developed by the United States. The period of 1980-1990 was termed as the golden age in the development of the maritime drones and unmanned naval technology, because during this period many theoretical developments were been implemented in the practical areas. Then from 1990-2000, there was further development made in unmanned technological domain to meet the objectives and number of organizations were able during this period to develop drones to meet their goals and objectives. During 2000-2010, there was seen the commercialization of the Maritime unmanned systems or drones as well as the development of the Cooperative motion control technology and there was the proper use of the unmanned technology in the practical field. This means that, with the passage of time, advancements in sensor technologies, and other unmanned systems successfully transformed the capacities of the unmanned technologies (BURSUC, MUNTEANU, & RUS, 2024).

So, the history of the unmanned naval technology reveals that development of these systems faces both successes and failures that provided lessons for the later designs. Today, many states are in the process of acquiring these unmanned systems and many states are using these in warfare, for example, Ukraine’s use of unmanned technology against Russia in the Black Sea. Because, these systems not only provide surveillance and operational effectiveness in warfare but also very cost-effective as compared to large-manned vessels. These technologies transformed the

naval battlefield and will continue to do so as new technologies will emerge.

UNMANNED TECHNOLOGY TRANSFORMING THE NAVAL WARFARE:

The advent of the unmanned systems has caused a profound transformation of the naval warfare landscape. These unmanned and autonomous ships including large unmanned surface vessels, unmanned underwater vessels, unmanned aerial vessels, small drone boats, etc. are revolutionizing the naval operations as they offer enhanced endurance, surveillance, versatility, and most importantly cost-effective advantages (Bansal, 2024).

The incorporation of robotics, artificial intelligence and remotely controlled systems in the naval warfare landscape is marking a new point in naval warfare history where AI enabled and unmanned systems are playing leading role in maritime defense strategies. This is the technological shift in naval warfare that is not only transforming the operational tactics of the navies around the world but also in the process of redefining the future of the naval conflicts as well as the security.

Primarily, the unmanned technologies were used for the seaborne targets or for the purpose of Oceanographic surveying. But in the contemporary world, they are now used for more dangerous and more complex operations and tasks such as antisubmarine warfare, mine warfare, etc. Many reports are indicating the increased use of the unmanned systems especially USVs in various missions around the world (The Rise of Robotics and Autonomous Systems in Naval Warfare, n.d.).

Contemporary trends in drone development

As the use of unmanned systems in naval warfare is increasing in the contemporary world and these technologies are more advanced (Boretti, 2024), some states are on the way of integrating and operating the hybrid fleets, meaning that they combine conventional warships and drones. Here is an evolution of the network communications purposed to improve or promote command and control between drones or unmanned systems and human operators.

Naval forces of many states have invested to develop UAVs, UUVs and USVs. The main aim of

developing these technologies is that they can replace the conventional naval assets such as submarines, destroyers, etc. in order to perform complex missions with more accuracy, precision, and less or no human loss. Naval forces are also investing and on the way of developing more advanced technologies such as, quantum encrypted communication networks, AI-enabled machine learning algorithms, and other unmanned systems with capabilities that can perform missions without human intervention. The most important technology and strategy that is in the phase of becoming popular used in the modern naval warfare is the multi domain swarming (Mukherjee, 2024).

Likewise, the C5ISRT systems (Command, Control, Computing, Communications, Cyber, Intelligence, Surveillance, Reconnaissance and Targeting) are also been developing in order to enhance the effectiveness of the battlespace or to maintain the superiority in battlespace in the more contested maritime environments.

As unmanned technologies become more widespread and advanced (Boretti, 2024), the proactive deployment of these defensive measures is becoming imperative. This strategic approach aims to reduce risks, protect vital assets, and bolster the Navy's flexibility in adapting to the evolving dynamics of contemporary naval warfare. This initiative aligns with broader goals of upholding maritime security and contributing to regional stability amid rapidly shifting conditions in warfare.

Drone Arms Race:

As unmanned technologies are developing, countries are seeking to acquire drones and unmanned systems more than their rivals in order to gain economic and strategic advantages. So, with the advent and use of unmanned technologies, a new drone arms race has been started between the states like US, Russia and China. The major implications of this drone arms race are emphasizing the concerns of security and privacy as well as potential for escalation of conflicts. So there is need for the rules and regulations at the international level in order to prevent the misuse of these drones and also that there increased proliferation must not destabilize the international peace and security (Boyle, 2015).

Naval warfare is under continuous transformation process with the increased usage of unmanned technologies and it is evident in the enhanced usage of USVs arising from smaller scale usage in 2010s in Yemen and full-scale use of USV in 2023 by Ukraine (Bischoff, 2023). Similarly, UUVs and Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVS) are significant for missions like Mine countermeasures, anti-submarine warfare, intelligence and surveillance. These vessels can operate in high-risk environments and without putting manned assets at risk. These technologies are expanding rapidly, especially in the regions like Strait of Hormuz and South China Sea. States like U.S., China and Russia are heavily investing underwater platforms because of their increased strategic and economic benefits (BURSUC, MUNTEANU, & RUS, 2024). These unmanned systems are challenging the existing norms and revolutionizing the maritime theatre. Additionally, naval unmanned technologies will not only support the protection of critical infrastructure, provide situational awareness, protective screens for large vessels like aircraft carriers, provide advance warnings but also create deterrence against enemies in near future. Also, in anti-submarine warfare, these unmanned systems will redefine the underwater conflicts by tracking the submarines of enemies effectively (Bischoff, 2023).

Implications for Crisis Stability:

The deployment of unmanned devices may enable authorities to act more aggressively during the time of crisis. Without the fear of human losses, military leaders may feel more confident in their use of autonomous vehicles than they would do with the manned systems. For instance, because of lesser concerns of exposure, UUVs would employ active sonar to locate hostile vessels. One strategy to help limit the risk of accidental escalation caused by unplanned contacts at sea is to build effective diplomatic channels that enable each party to rapidly ascertain the other's intent in such situations.

Challenging Traditional Naval Operations:

At the center of this technological transformation in the naval warfare is the erosion of the domination and supremacy of the large surface vessels. The reason is that, naval drones provide versatility, reliability, cost-effectiveness, precision strikes and

most importantly do all operations more effectively without risking human lives. So, in the modern naval warfare, these technologies would be preferred and boundaries of the traditional targeting as well as the reconnaissance are becoming less significant.

These all lessons can be learnt from the Black Sea in case of the Russia-Ukraine conflict. In Black Sea, Ukraine used USVs that helped Ukraine to strike on Russian Naval targets without having strong traditional navy, and also caused Russian Black Sea fleet pushed back out of the range of the unmanned systems of Ukraine (Bischoff, 2023).

CASE STUDY OF UKRAINE:

Russia made unjustified invasion of Ukraine in 2022. This has created the necessity for developing as well as testing of technologies. As at the most initial stage of the conflict, Ukraine's huge part of naval forces has lost, so there was need for Ukraine to develop some new technologies in order to defend itself from Russia's attacks. Ukraine surprised Russia repeatedly when Ukraine developed unmanned naval vessels especially USVs that were also able to be used for the offensive operations (BURSUC, MUNTEANU, & RUS, 2024).

The strategic deployment of Ukraine's USVs, especially MAGURA V5 model, was a transformative factor in its naval warfare against Russia and it achieved remarkable tactical successes. In Black Sea, these USVs that were termed as Kamikaze USVs (KUSVs) damaged almost 10 Russian vessels and underscored Russian vessels' effectiveness in the asymmetric naval warfare. This success of Ukrainian KUSVs has forced Russia to adopt a more defensive posture and become more cautious regarding fleet deployments in the Black Sea (Bansal, 2024).

So, the efforts of Ukraine to push Russia back in the Black Sea, strengthened by the Western aid, have not only challenged the status quo but also reshaped the security landscape of the region. Ukraine succeeded in the Black Sea against Russia by using the asymmetric tactics, including USVs, land-based missile systems, etc. Supported by the western allies, these tools have enabled Ukraine to attack the high valued Russian naval vessels even without direct ship to ship combat. According to an estimate by the observers, since February, 2022, Ukraine despite its limited naval capabilities, has destroyed almost half

of the Russian Black Sea Fleet, decreasing it from eighty warships to forty warships through successful usage of unmanned vessels. This loss of Russia's Black Fleet has decreased its operational capabilities and forced many Russian naval vessels into long term repairs. For instance, in April 2022, Ukrainian Neptune missiles has sunk Moskva (Russian Black Sea Fleet Flagship) and this was the operational as well as symbolic blow to Russia. This attack not only caused disruptions in Russia's naval superiority and its naval actions in the black sea but also demonstrated capacities or unmanned naval capabilities of Ukraine.

Sea drones have played significant role in the naval strategy of Ukraine, and this is illustrated by their strikes on the Russian warships, like strike in august 2023 on Olenegoskiy Gorniyak (Russia's landing vessel). Ukraine's Unmanned Systems offer many advantages like cost-effectiveness, more operational efficiency against Russian naval operations and most importantly perform actions without even risking Ukraine's personnel (Lyashenko, 2024).

Major attacks on Russian naval forces: Turning the tide

Ukraine, as previously mentioned carried out a series of attacks that severely harmed and weakened the Black Sea Fleet of Russia, and this has transformed the dynamics of the conflict in the Black Sea. Some of the Ukraine's attacks on Russia's crucial assets includes the sinking of Moskva, that was the flagship of Russia's Black Sea Fleet in April 2022. Another attack carried out by Ukraine was the attack or missile strike on the Sevastopol Shipyard with 10 cruise missiles and 3 unmanned boats in September 2023 (voanews, 2023), that not only damaged Minsk (landing ship) and Rostov-on-Don (submarine), but also caused many casualties of the Russian personnel. The other attack by Ukraine in September 2023, included the strike on the Russia's Black Sea Fleet headquarters that further caused harms to the naval command structure of Russia and also caused further limitation of the Russian operational capabilities.

All these as well as other attacks that Ukraine carried out not only weakened Black Sea Fleet of Russia but also forced Russia to must revise its naval strategy in order to ensure defense from Ukraine's attacks.

These attacks significantly decreased the Russia's naval capabilities and prevented Russia's influence in Black Sea. This also shifted the dynamics of the conflict in Ukraine's favor in naval or maritime domain (Lyashenko, 2024).

Overall, the argument is that relentless strikes and drone using in warfare by Ukraine has forced Russia's Black Sea Fleet, once a dominant force, to withdraw from the occupied Crimea and has diminished Russia's naval strength in the Black Sea. In 2024, announcement made by Ukraine that Russia has finally pulled its last patrol boat from Crimea and Russia's Black Sea Fleet has push back out of the range of Ukraine's unmanned systems. These all attacks and strikes carried out successfully by western allies' provided cruise missiles as well as the domestically built unmanned systems or drones. Even though, Ukraine was lacking the conventional navy but achievements were made by the use of advanced technologies including the unmanned systems that completely changed the conflict dynamics (Kirichenko, 2024).

Looking Forward, the ambitious plan of Ukraine to make 1 million drones in coming years present a strong commitment leveraging the drones or the unmanned technology in the military doctrine of Ukraine. This with further enhance the operational capabilities of Ukraine (Bansal, 2024).

RECOMMENDATIONS:

- Update International laws as well as regional laws in order to ensure rules and regulations related to the use of unmanned technologies
- Ensure ethical guidelines for using unmanned or autonomous weapons during naval operation, keeping in view the protection of civilians
- Develop the monitoring systems and mechanisms in order to ensure the legal frameworks
- Address the environmental effects of using the unmanned systems more importantly
- Promote awareness on unmanned naval warfare

CONCLUSION:

Since ancient ages, wars are being fought with three distinct components; weapons, strategies and soldiers. The latter has always remained of most importance in all generations of warfare, as

development of strategies and weaponization of armies remain totally dependent upon the risk to lives of the combatants. However, now the basic essence of warfare is being revolutionized as the human element is being taken out of the battlefield. There used to be a fairly stable tradition of war but unmanned systems have totally changed everything. The safety to the soldiers' lives has provided huge flexibility to military strategists for taking risks and operating well beyond their earlier limitations.

World navies are endeavoring to utilize all domains of the Unmanned systems, e.g., UAVs, USVs, and UUVs to accomplish assigned missions. However, most developments in military usage of the Unmanned systems are evident in the fields of aerial platforms. The successful use of Unmanned systems with no risk to human lives have generated an enormous pace among the world navies to transform unmanned technologies in other dimensions of naval warfare. Leading naval powers have already inducted several unmanned systems into their fleets. The advancements in the unmanned technologies are paving the way for the future where autonomous systems will play a crucial role in maintaining the maritime deterrence as well as maritime security. The use of these unmanned systems especially USVs is seen in many conflicts, like in the current Russia-Ukraine conflict, where it becomes evident that without having large conventional forces, states can gain edge using these unmanned systems in the naval operations, as Ukraine did against Russia in the Black Sea.

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